

Sensitive Data Toolkit for Researchers

Part 1: Glossary of Terms for Sensitive Data used for Research Purposes

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Alliance** of Canada

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Introduction

The Sensitive Data Expert Group of the Digital Research Alliance of Canada has created a suite of tools for Canadian researchers. These tools have been created to help researchers understand how research data are involved in the research ethics process, and to address the evolution of research data management (RDM) practices such as data sharing and deposit in the context of existing research ethics frameworks.

This tool, the Glossary of Terms for Sensitive Data used for Research Purposes, is intended to provide definitions for a number of common terms used in the discussion of the management of sensitive data in the Canadian context. These definitions have been informed by the *Tri-Council Policy Statement: Ethical Conduct for Research Involving Humans* ([TCPS2](#)), the Consortia Advancing Standards in Research Administration Information and CODATA ([CODATA](#)), and other sources. Some definitions are kept from a previous version of the toolkit (DOI: [10.5281/zenodo.4060158](#)), which drew from a variety of institutional sources.

Glossary

Note that these definitions are intended to facilitate use of the Sensitive Data Toolkit. They are not intended to supersede definitions that apply to specific use cases (e.g. a definition from the TCPS2 would supersede any definition here in discussions with an institutional research ethics board). Additionally, these terms will have specific definitions where they appear in legislation, and may vary from jurisdiction to jurisdiction (notably, as an example, Personal Health Information).

Access: Continued availability and ongoing usability of a digital resource, retaining all qualities of authenticity, accuracy and functionality deemed to be essential for the purposes the digital material was created and/or acquired for. Users who have access can retrieve, understand, manipulate, and store copies. Data access is an important aspect of research data management.

Access controls: Processes and procedures to limit or control the ability to see, download or use a dataset or other digital resource. These might include application procedures, or technical barriers/solutions.

Administrative data: Information originally collected for non-research purposes. These types of data are collected by government or other organizations for a variety of purposes, often during the delivery of a service. These data are also recognized as having research value (e.g. tax records, graduation records, vital statistics). These data are almost always collected without participants consent for use in research.

Aggregated data: Information that has been summarized at the level of the entire dataset or for selected subgroups of the entire dataset. In aggregated data, each row of data represents a number of observations from an original dataset.

Anonymized data: Data that are irrevocably stripped of direct and indirect identifiers; a code is not kept to allow future re-linkage of data, and the risk of re-identification of individuals is very low. According to the [TCPS2 \(2022\)](#), secondary use of anonymized human participant data for research purposes requires Research Ethics Board (REB) review and clearance, unless allowed by original consent (“[Broad consent](#)”).

Anonymous data: Data that have never had direct identifiers from the point of original collection and where the risk of identification from indirect identifiers is low or very low. Note that according to Article 2.4, [TCPS2 \(2022\)](#), REB review is not required for research that relies exclusively on secondary use of anonymous human participant information, or anonymous human biological materials, so long as the process of data linkage, recording, or dissemination of results does not generate identifiable information.

Authorized data access: When personnel (as individuals or according to role) are given access to data by the researcher.

CARE Principles: Set of principles for Indigenous data governance. CARE stands for Collective benefit, Authority to control, Responsibility and Ethics. These principles complement the FAIR principles.

Cloud Services: A method of storing and sharing data by way of remote servers accessed from the Internet. Cloud services are maintained, operated and managed by a cloud service provider on storage servers. Cloud services can be public or private. While any use of cloud services comes with some inherent risk, the risks for public and private servers are different. Some main differences include server location, server control, and potential vulnerabilities.

- **Public cloud services** are companies that provide free or for-fee storage to multiple customers using remote servers that are managed by a provider. Data are stored on the provider’s server and the provider is responsible for the management and maintenance of the data center. Examples of public cloud services include Google Drive, DropBox, iCloud and OneDrive. Of particular note to Canadian academic institutions, public cloud storage is provided using servers that are outside of the institution’s control and that could be anywhere in the world, and thus subject to the host country’s laws. Public clouds often have large infrastructure with many different points where an unauthorized user could attempt to extract data. These services often also employ user data in training AI models. Unencrypted sensitive data should never be stored in a public cloud and researchers should think carefully about storing encrypted sensitive data in a public cloud. Some provinces have stricter conditions around placing sensitive data in public cloud services.
- **Community cloud services** are cloud storage available and offered at no or low cost to researchers. They are operated by a community and funded by government or a community funding model.
- **Private cloud services** store data on internal servers using local infrastructure. A private cloud is not shared with any other organization. Management of and access to data stored in private cloud services is controlled by the home institution or organization. Private clouds may offer an increased level of security as they share

very few, if any, resources with other organizations. However; not all institutions have the infrastructure and/or personnel needed to host private services.

Confidential data: Information entrusted to a person, organization or entity with the intent that it be kept private and access to that information be controlled or restricted.

Cybersecurity: Any technologies, practices and policies for protecting computer systems, applications, devices, data, financial assets and people against malicious actors.

Data: Facts, measurements, recordings, records, or observations about the world. Data may be in any format or medium and take many forms, including: writings, notes, numbers, symbols, text, images, films, video, sound recordings, pictorial reproductions, drawings, designs or other graphical representations, procedural manuals, forms, diagrams, work flow charts, equipment descriptions, data files, data processing algorithms, or statistical records.

Data custodian/steward: An individual or organization responsible for providing and protecting data in conformity with the policies and practices prescribed by data governance. This role is not standardized and a data custodian/steward could have a number of roles and duties related to the curation, preservation and sharing of data.

Data deposit: Publishing data into a recognized repository for preservation and/or possible re-use by other researchers.

Data lifecycle: All of the stages in the existence of data from collection to destruction. A lifecycle view is used to enable active management of data over time, thus maintaining security, accessibility, and utility.

Data linkage: The process of combining data from different sources. This may raise privacy concerns, especially when it involves identifiable information.

Data management plan (DMP): A document describing how research data will be managed throughout a specified research project's life cycle - during and after the active phase of the research project - including terms regarding archiving and potential preservation of the data in a data repository. Additionally, DMPs generally include some metadata and policies for data access, re-use and redistribution. The DMP is considered to be a 'living' document, i.e. one which can be updated when necessary.

Data repository: A type of a sustainable information infrastructure which provides long-term storage and access to research data. Ideally, materials in data repositories are curated and stewarded to ensure they are authentic, discoverable, and appropriately accessible over the medium term. Some repositories may be suitable for sensitive data.

Data sharing: The practice of making data available for discovery and reuse. This may be done by depositing the data in a repository for access or through other means of data publication. Data sharing may be subject to conditions and limitations, particularly when data are sensitive, subject to legal or regulatory requirements, or when data are proprietary in nature.

De-identification: The act of changing individual-level data to decrease the probability of disclosing an individual's identity. This can involve masking direct identifiers (e.g., name,

phone number, address) as well as transforming (e.g., recoding, combining) or suppressing indirect identifiers that could be used alone or in combination to identify an individual (e.g., birth dates, geographic details, dates of key events). If done correctly, de-identification minimizes risk of re-identification of any data shared or released.

Deletion: The process of destroying data stored on hard disks, mobile devices and other forms of electronic media so that they become completely unreadable and cannot be recovered, accessed or used. This is different from what is commonly understood by “delete” and is sometimes referred to as “shredding” or “secure deletion”.

Digital preservation (or Archiving): The active process of managing digital content over time. This process involves activities such as selecting content for preservation, preparing and maintaining it in formats and environments that ensure ongoing usability, and implementing strategies to ensure long-term access. Digital archiving is sometimes used synonymously with digital preservation.

Disclosure: Disclosure relates to the inappropriate attribution of information to a data subject, whether an individual or an organisation.

Encryption: A method of scrambling data so that only authorized parties can understand the information. In technical terms, it is the process of converting human-readable plaintext to incomprehensible text, also known as ciphertext. In simpler terms, encryption takes readable data and alters them so that they appear random. Encryption requires the use of a cryptographic key: a set of mathematical values that both the sender and the recipient of an encrypted message agree on.

Harm: Negative consequences or effects to the welfare of individuals, groups, or entities. The nature of harm may include social, behavioural, psychological, physical, economic, ecological, or legal consequences. Harm also includes impact on privacy, security, reputation and status. When collecting sensitive data and considering their storage, maintenance, and possible secondary use, the potential for both immediate and future harms should be carefully considered.

Identifying information (or Personal Information): Information that identifies an individual, organization, or entity; or information for which it is reasonably foreseeable, under given circumstances, that either alone or with other information, could make such an identification.

Directly identifying information (or direct identifiers): Information that identifies a specific individual, organization or entity through a unique characteristic (e.g., name, address, social insurance number).

Indirectly identifying information (or indirect identifiers): Information that, while not directly identifying, when used or considered in combination with other information, could reasonably be expected to identify an individual, organization or entity (e.g., education level, age, postal code, or demographic characteristics).

Personal health information: Identifying information about an individual in oral or recorded form, if the information:

- (a) relates to the physical or mental health of the individual, including information that consists of the health history of the individual's family,
- (b) relates to the provision of health care to the individual, including the identification of a person as a provider of health care to that individual,
- (c) is a plan of service within the meaning of the Home Care and Community Services Act, 1994 for the individual,
- (d) relates to payments or eligibility for health care, or eligibility for coverage for health care, in respect to the individual,
- (e) relates to the donation by the individual of any body part or bodily substance, or is derived from the testing or examination of any such body part or bodily substance,
- (f) contains the individual's health number, or
- (g) identifies an individual's substitute decision-maker.

Note that the assessment of whether information is identifiable is made in the context of the specific research.

Institutional Research Board (IRB): See Research Ethics Board.

Linkage: The combining of two or more datasets with a common element or elements to provide further information in a new dataset. Note that growing numbers of databases and advancing technological capacity to link databases create new research opportunities, but also new privacy risks. In particular, linkage of de-identified or anonymized databases may result in re-identification of individuals. Article 5.7 of the [TCPS2](#) requires that researchers seek REB review and approval prior to linking datasets obtained from human participant research.

Metadata: Literally, "data about data". Data that define and describe the characteristics of other data, used to improve both understanding of data and data-related processes. It is important to note that sometimes metadata can be identifying (directly or indirectly). For example, a photo's metadata might contain the coordinates where it was taken, a survey record might contain the IP address of the computer on which the survey was filled. Ensure that metadata do not potentially identify individuals or entities that should not be identified.

OCAP®: The First Nations principles of OCAP® establish how First Nations' data and information will be collected, protected, used, or shared. Standing for ownership, control, access and possession, OCAP® is a tool to support strong information governance on the path to First Nations data sovereignty. Given the diversity within and across Nations, the principles will be expressed and asserted in line with a Nation's respective world view, traditional knowledge, and protocols.

Online survey software: Software used by researchers to collect data from participants through questionnaires completed over the internet, usually through web forms connected to

a database where the answers are stored. Researchers and participants should be aware of the privacy and security policies of specific software platforms and providers.

Open access (OA): A set of principles and range of practices through which research outputs are distributed online with limited or no barriers to access. Any kind of digital content can be OA, from texts and data, to software, audio, video, and multimedia. While most of these are related to text only, a growing number of OA sources are integrating text with images, data, and executable code. OA can also apply to non-scholarly content, like music, movies, and novels.

Open data: Structured data that are accessible, machine-readable, usable, intelligible, and freely shared. Open data can be freely used, re-used, built on, and redistributed by anyone - subject, at most, to the requirement to attribute and sharealike.

Portable storage device: Any device or media which is easily transportable, upon which information can be stored. This definition is not restricted to purpose built storage devices such as physical media, external hard drives, and USB flash drives; but also may include laptop computers, tablets, smart phones, wearable technology (e.g., VR headset, fitbit, smart watches) and any other portable computing device. Portable storage devices can be either internet-connected or non-networked, and different data security measures will apply in each case.

Primary research data: Information collected by a researcher from first-hand sources (e.g., directly from research participants), for the specific purpose of the research question at hand.

Privacy: The individual right to be free from unwanted intrusion or interference by others. It's a core principle in societies that value freedom and democracy. This right extends to one's body, personal information, thoughts, opinions, communications, and personal spaces. Privacy also involves the ability to control one's own information, which is closely linked to the concept of consent. Privacy is maintained when individuals have the opportunity to manage their personal information by giving or withholding consent for its collection, use, and disclosure. Research can impact privacy differently depending on its goals and methods.

Privacy Impact Assessment: A process to evaluate how a project or system might affect the privacy of individuals, and to determine measures to mitigate risks.

Processed data: Data that have been selected, modified, cleaned, or transformed from raw data in order to support a research project or question.

Pseudonymization: The process of assigning a fictional name or alias (a pseudonym) to a specific person, group or place. In research, the process of pseudonymization is a type of de-identification used to help protect the identity of research participants, and organizations or entities involved in research.

Public facing: A resource which accepts anonymous connection requests from any public internet protocol address.

Publicly available information: Some types of information are available to the public in a certain form and for a certain purpose, as specified by laws or regulations. For example: registries of deaths, court judgments, or public archives and publicly available statistics (e.g., Statistics Canada files). In Canada, all publicly available archives (national, provincial or municipal) have policies governing access to their records. An archival record or database that is subject to restrictions, such as those under access to information and privacy legislation, may also be considered publicly available.

Raw data: Data that have not been processed for meaningful use. Although raw data have the potential to become "information", they require selective extraction, organization, and sometimes analysis and formatting for presentation. Unless raw data are anonymous, they have yet to be de-identified and might therefore be considered sensitive.

Research data: Data that are used as primary sources to support technical or scientific enquiry, research, scholarship, or artistic activity, and that are used as evidence in the research process and/or are commonly accepted in the research community as necessary to validate research findings and results.

Research data management: An active process including, but not limited to, standards and practices related to data collection, metadata, storage, licensing, ethics, discovery, sharing, preservation, and reuse.

Research Ethics Board (REB): A committee that reviews research proposals to ensure ethical standards are met, particularly regarding participant safety and confidentiality sometimes referred to as an IRB (Institutional Review Board).

Restricted data (Controlled access data): Data that are not immediately accessible due to commercial, ethical or legal reasons or are available upon request.

Risk: The potential for harm to individuals, communities, organizations or entities. Risk is a function of the magnitude or seriousness of the harm, and the probability that it will occur, whether to research participants or to third parties. Consideration of risk should encompass immediate harm, delayed harm and downstream harm.

Extreme risk data: Data which require the strongest controls against unauthorized disclosure, loss, and/or modification that would almost certainly result in severe harm.

High risk data: Data which require strong controls against unauthorized disclosure, loss, and/or modification that could result in significant harm.

Medium risk data: Data which requires controls against unauthorized disclosure, loss, and modification and in most cases is considered confidential. Disclosure, loss, or unauthorized modification of confidential information may result in putting research participants in moderate harm.

Low risk data: Data which if disclosed are unlikely to cause harm to participants.

Secondary data: Pre-existing information, usually collected or generated by an entity other than the researcher, for purposes other than the current research objective.

Security: The measures taken to protect information, encompassing physical, administrative, and technical safeguards. Physical security includes things such as locking file cabinets and restricting access to data storage locations. Administrative security involves establishing rules for who can access information. Technical security includes using passwords, firewalls, anti-virus software, and encryption to prevent unauthorized access, loss, or modification of data. These security measures support the fulfillment of confidentiality obligations.

Sensitive data: Data that cannot be shared without potentially breaking the law, or violating the trust of, or risking harm to, an individual, entity, or community.

Traditional knowledge/Indigenous sensitive data: Knowledge held by the Indigenous peoples of Canada, that is, First Nations, Inuit, and Métis peoples. Traditional knowledge is specific to place, and rooted in the experience of multiple generations. It is determined by an Indigenous community's land, environment, region, culture, and language. Traditional knowledge is usually described by Indigenous peoples as holistic, involving body, mind, feelings, and spirit. Knowledge may be expressed in symbols, arts, ceremonial and everyday practices, narratives and, especially, in relationships. It includes preserved knowledge created by, and received from, past generations and innovations and new knowledge transmitted to subsequent generations. In international or scholarly discourse, the terms "traditional knowledge" and "Indigenous knowledge" are sometimes used interchangeably.

TCPS2: The *Tri-Council Policy Statement: Ethical Conduct for Research Involving Humans* (TCPS or the Policy) is a joint policy of Canada's three federal research agencies – the Canadian Institutes of Health Research (CIHR), the Natural Sciences and Engineering Research Council of Canada (NSERC), and the Social Sciences and Humanities Research Council (SSHRC). The Policy provides the principles and guidelines that govern the ethical conduct of human participant research in Canadian institutions eligible to receive funding from the three federal agencies noted. This policy extends to all human participant research conducted under the auspices and/or jurisdiction of the institution.

Vulnerable Populations: Populations that are at greater risk of harm in research contexts, and require additional ethical considerations. What constitutes a vulnerable population will vary across contexts and can be situational.